

CERAMICS IN EUROPE

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ICC9

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Invited presentation:

Mesoporous nanoparticles doped with ions with potential therapeutic effect: synthesis and characterization

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Abstract:

Mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) are attracting significant attention as suitable materials for multifunctional biomedical applications, as suitable vehicles for drug delivery, and controlled release of ions with potential therapeutic effect. In the present work, we report on our activities in the preparation and characterization of mesoporous nanoparticles in the system CaO-SiO₂, doped with various amounts of metallic ions, such as Ce, Ga, and Zn. Various methods of dopant incorporation are examined, and the influence of synthesis conditions on morphology, pore structure, specific surface, and solubility of the nanoparticles is evaluated. Ce- and Ga- doped systems exhibit bioactivity in-vitro, documented by precipitation of phosphate phases upon immersion in a simulated body fluid. The Zn-doping inhibits the formation of hydroxycarbonate apatite (HCAp). The Ce-MBGNPs are non-cytotoxic toward pre-osteoblast MC3T3-E1 cells in direct contact with nanoparticles up to a concentration of 100 µg/mL. The nanoparticles decrease the release of nitric oxide, indicating the anti-inflammatory response tested with lipopolysaccharides (LPS)-induced proinflammatory RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. Ce- and Ga-containing MBGNPs show antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* without exhibiting cytotoxicity towards MG-63 osteoblast-like cells. Zn-MBGNs improve the differentiation of the MG-63 osteoblast-like cells, also showing a higher ability to adsorb proteins than their undoped counterparts. Due to their advantageous morphological and physiochemical properties, the prepared nanoparticles show promise as bioactive fillers in a variety of applications including bone regeneration and wound healing.

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